

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02

Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS 3

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY 4

DATA PROTECTION IN EU RESEARCH 5

1.1 APPLICABLE LEGAL FRAMEWORK 5

1.2 PRINCIPLES OF PERSONAL DATA PROCESSING 5

INFORMED CONSENT PROCEDURES 8

DATA PROCESSING 9

APPENDIX 1 – DECLARATIONS ON HORIZON EUROPE ETHICAL STANDARDS AND DATA PROTECTION11

APPENDIX 2 – DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS45

APPENDIX 3 – INFORMED CONSENT USED FOR EVENTS PARTICIPATION.....46

APPENDIX 4 - INFORMED CONSENT USED FOR ONLINE SURVEYS56

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current document has been developed within the framework of the MARINEWIND project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement No 101075572.

The purpose of this Deliverable is to provide detailed information on the technical, security and organizational measures that will be implemented by the MARINEWIND consortium to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants, in particular those related to **personal data protection**. To this end, the present document defines the data protection rights of participants to MARINEWIND activities, describes data processing procedures used by the consortium, and applicable legislation as well as includes informed consent templates that will be used during the project implementation.

The information contained in this document will represent a key point of reference for all project activities that will involve humans, such as:

- Participation in all project events (co-creation workshops, webinars, meetings, etc.),
- Participation in interviews/surveys (online and in person) run by the project.

The document also contains information about the **Data Protection Officers (DPO)** of each Beneficiary and Associated Partners required to appoint a DPO under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹ and their contact details (Appendix 2).

The way data protection and privacy issues are considered and formally treated depends on the legal environment of each country where the activities will take place. However, despite the various differences across the EU Member States legal frameworks, the application of the GDPR guarantees a coherent approach towards these issues. To confirm compliance with EU and national data protection rules, each MARINEWIND Beneficiary and Associated Partner signed a '**Declaration on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection**' (Appendix 1).

Moreover, the present deliverable provides information concerning the privacy policy and data protection rights related to the **functioning of the MARINEWIND website** and the **MARINEWIND tools**.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC

DATA PROTECTION IN EU RESEARCH

1.1 APPLICABLE LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The European Union has developed the EU Data Protection and Privacy legal framework,² which aims at ensuring that personal data enjoy a high standard of protection everywhere in the EU and that persons or organizations collecting and managing personal information must protect it from misuse. One of the main pillars of this legal framework is Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR). The Regulation applies to all entities established in the EU (or branches established in the EU) that process personal data as part of their activities, regardless of where the data is processed, and entities established outside the EU offering goods/services to individuals in the EU or monitoring the behavior in the EU of these individuals.

In addition to GDPR, there are other sectorial legal acts that must be considered when implementing EU research projects:

- Regulation (EC) N° 45/2001 of the European Parliament and the Council of 18 December 2000 in the protection of individuals regarding the processing of personal data by the Community institutions and bodies and on the free movement of such data;
- Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purpose of prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences;
- Directive 2000/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2000 on certain legal aspects of information society services, in particular electronic commerce in the Internal Market;
- Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector.

Since MARINEWIND activities involve processing personal data, the GDPR and the above legal acts shall be complied with and respected by the consortium as a whole and by each project Beneficiary and Associated Partners which will deal with personal data processing in the context of project implementation. To confirm compliance with the applicable EU and national legislation, each MARINEWIND Beneficiary and Associated Partners signed a '**Declaration on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection**' (all signed declarations are presented in Appendix 1).

1.2 Principles of personal data processing

According to Art. 4(1) of GDPR, **personal data** 'means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified,

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection_en

directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person'. Personal data protection typically covers: names and surnames, home and email address, an identification card number, location data and IP address or a cookie ID. **Processing of personal data** is defined in Art. 4(2) of the Regulation and means 'any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction'.

In its Art. 5, the GDPR provides for the **principles of personal data processing**, stating that personal data must be:

- 'processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject ('lawfulness, fairness and transparency');
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes (...) ('purpose limitation');
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed ('data minimization');
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that inaccurate personal data, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay ('accuracy');
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed (...) ('storage limitation');
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorized or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organizational measures ('integrity and confidentiality').

In order to fulfill the GDPR requirements, there is a set of indications that each MARINEWIND Beneficiary and Associated Partners, dealing with data processing, will respect during the project implementation:

1) Consent

The consent should be given by an individual (data subject) in a free, specific, informed and unambiguous manner, by way of a request presented in clear and plain language. Moreover, the consent should be given by an affirmative act, such as checking a box online or signing a form (this methodology is explained in Section 2 of this deliverable).

2) Providing transparent information

Individuals must be clearly informed on who is processing their personal data as well as what data will be processed, why and how. In addition to the above information, individuals should be also informed about who will receive the data, how long the data will be stored, the individual's data protection rights

(i.e., right to access, correct, erase, restrict, object, portability, etc.), whether there is a statutory or contractual obligation to provide the data and how consent can be withdrawn.

3) Ensuring the right to access and the right to data portability

Individuals must have the right to request access to their personal data, free of charge and in an accessible format. In addition, when the processing is based on consent or a contract, the individual can ask for their personal data to be returned or transmitted to another company (right to portability).

4) Ensuring the right to erasure (right to be forgotten)

An individual has the right to request the data controller to erase their personal data, such as when the data is no longer needed to fulfil the processing purpose. The data controller is not obliged to comply with such request if: the processing is necessary to respect one's freedom of expression and information, they must keep the personal data to comply with a legal obligation; there are other reasons of public interest to keep the personal data, such as public health or scientific and historical research purposes; they need to keep the personal data to establish a legal claim.

5) Ensuring the right to correct and right to object

If an individual thinks that their personal data is incorrect, incomplete or inaccurate, they have the right to have it rectified or completed without undue delay

6) Obligation to appoint a Data Protection Officer

An entity must appoint a DPO when: it regularly or systematically monitors individuals or process special categories of data; this processing is a core business activity, and it does it on a large scale. In the case of MARINEWIND Beneficiaries, all relevant declarations are provided in Appendix 1 to this deliverable, and the list of DPOs with their contact details is provided in Appendix 2.

7) Obligation of data protection by design and by default

In order to minimize privacy risks and increase trust, a data controller³ must take all necessary steps (e.g. pseudonymization) to implement the data protection principles and protect the rights of individuals (data protection by design). In accordance with the obligation of data protection by default, the entity processing personal data should ensure that the most privacy friendly setting is the default setting.

8) Obligation to provide proper notification in the case of a data breach

In case a data breach occurs, and the breach poses a risk to individual rights and freedoms, the entity processing personal data should notify the relevant Data Protection Authority within 72 hours after

³ According to Art. 4(7) GDPR, 'controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law.

becoming aware of the breach. If the data breach poses a high risk to those affected, the entity may also be required to inform all individuals affected by the data breach.

Details on specific measures that will be taken by each MARINEWIND Beneficiary and Associated Partners to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants and the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorized access to their personal data are provided in Appendix 1 in the 'Declaration on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection' of each Beneficiary and Associated Partner, in the part related to the privacy policy of the Beneficiary and Associated Partner.

INFORMED CONSENT PROCEDURES

Participation in the MARINEWIND project is voluntary, and individual participants agree to participate in project activities (both online and physical) based on the invitation issued in advance. Participants receive an informed consent (see Appendix 3 and Appendix 4) to read and agree to participate, before the commencement of any project activity requiring their involvement, in compliance with GDPR.

The documentation related to informed consent will be provided in the language and terms intelligible to the participants. To this end, the relevant informed consents have been prepared in English, Italian, Portuguese, French, Spanish and Greek with the option to provide other language-specific format when required (see Appendix 3 and Appendix 4). Before each event involving participants, they will be asked to sign an informed consent and will be fully briefed, in the informed consent, as to their data protection rights, including:

- who is responsible for the treatment of data;
- who is the data protection officer to whom the participant can claim their rights;
- specification of which data we are collecting (personal data or other);
- how the consortium will deal with the data (collection, storage, etc.);
- for which purpose we are collecting data (research and no other purpose; explicitly excluding commercial purpose);
- what are the consequences of the denial of the use of data;
- the possibility of withdrawing from the use of data and the consequences;
- to whom data will be transmitted;
- the time of storage of data;
- the place of storage and the tools available to guarantee security;
- the rights of the data owner (to access, modify, rectify, cancel data, right to object, and to ask restriction of processing);
- risks or benefits of participation.

Participants will not be placed in any situation in which there is a likelihood of physical, mental, or emotional harm. No sensitive data⁴ will be collected, processed, or stored.

⁴ Data relating to racial or ethnic origin, religious or philosophical beliefs, political opinion, health including biometric and genetic data, sexual preferences, data relating to criminal convictions and offences or related security measures.

Following the above rules, the following types of informed consent will be used within the MARINEWIND project:

- informed consent used for **events** (online and in-person) organized by the consortium partners – the template of this consent is included in Appendix 3 to this document,
- informed consent used for **surveys / interview** launched by project partners to implement their activities – the template of this consent is included in Appendix 2 to this document.

DATA PROCESSING

The data processed in MARINEWIND are divided into two categories:

- **Personal data** (i.e. name, surname, date of birth, gender, level of education, professional affiliation and contact information);
- **Professional views on the themes related to the project and discussed during project activities, excluding sensitive data.**

Personal data is necessary for ensuring a person's participation in the MARINEWIND project and to comply with mandatory legal obligations under European Union legislation, as well as for processing under consent and for the purposes of legitimate interests as follows:

- To process any application a person makes to participate in any of the MARINEWIND events or activities;
- To process any request for information supplied by the project and to ensure effective communication;
- To organize and promote project events and activities;
- To send health and safety and other relevant event information for any MARINEWIND events and activities that persons are participating in;
- To notify persons of events, activities, publications, and services that may be of interest to them.

Information about professional views on the themes related to the project will be collected solely for research purposes necessary to carry out project activities.

The above data collected from participants will be stored on computer media of the consortium partner collecting this data (typically, a partner organizing a given activity) and protected against unauthorized access and use according to the internal rules of the respective partner, which must be in line with applicable EU and national legislation (see Appendix 1).

Where possible, any identifiable information will be encrypted or minimized. That means that only strictly necessary data will be collected, processed, and stored.

The consortium will retain the collected data for as long as it is necessary:

- To carry out MARINEWIND events and activities;
- For establishment or defense of legal claims that could be made against the consortium;

- To comply with legal obligations under EU law.

Any data collected within the project will be kept for two years after the end of the project and will then be destroyed by each project partner in relation to the data they processed during the project duration.

Data will be held on secure servers within the European Economic Area with all reasonable technological and operation measures put in place to safeguard it from unauthorized access. More information about data management is included in deliverable D6.5 - *Data Management Plan*.

APPENDIX 1 – DECLARATIONS ON HORIZON EUROPE ETHICAL STANDARDS AND DATA PROTECTION

1) APRE

Rome, 14/02/2023

DECLARATION

on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing APRE, with seat in via Cavour 71 (Rome), hereby certify that APRE:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR).
- hereby confirm that APRE does not designate a Data Protection Officer because none of the criteria in Art. 37 sub. 1 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are met in the case of APRE. Nevertheless, APRE has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants.

Director

APRE Privacy Policy

Data controller

APRE phone number: +39 06 48939993 Via Cavour n.71, 00184 (ROME) Italy

In compliance with the GDPR and on the basis of its organization chart, APRE has defined and formalized an Organizational Model of privacy related liability aimed at the correct processing of personal data.

Beyond the above Organizational Model relating to liability on privacy matters, all those who are in charge of a project that provides for the processing of personal data are required to adopt an ad hoc policy tailored on the specific needs of the case (so-called Privacy by Design).

When processing personal data, authorized staff are required to observe the following general principles:

Dignity of the data subject, i.e. the natural person whom the personal data is about

- **Lawfulness, accuracy and transparency:** personal data must be processed in a lawful, accurate and transparent way, in order to guarantee to the data subject adequate security, including protection, through appropriate technical and organizational measures, from unauthorized or unlawful processing and from accidental loss, destruction or damage. With regard to transparency, all information intended for the public or to the data subject must be concise, easily accessible and easily understood; the language used must be simple and clear.
- **Purpose limitation:** the purposes of the processing must be certain, explicit and legitimate, and subsequently processed in a way that is not incompatible with such purposes (without prejudice to further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest or for scientific or historical research purposes; or for statistical purposes).
- **Data minimization:** the data collected must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary with respect to the purposes for which they are processed. Specifically, information systems and computer programs must be configured by minimizing the use of personal data, so as to exclude their processing when the purposes pursued in individual cases can be achieved through anonymous data or other appropriate ways to identify the data subject only in case of necessity ('necessity principle').
- **Accuracy:** the data processed must be accurate and, if necessary, updated, therefore all reasonable steps must be taken to delete or edit inaccurate data in relation to the purposes for which they are processed.
- **Retention limit:** the data processed must be stored in a form that allows identification of the data subject for a period not longer than the necessary to achieve the purposes for which they are collected and processed (unless specific law providing for archiving processing in the public interest or for scientific or historical research purposes, or for statistical purposes).
- **Integrity and confidentiality:** the data must be processed in such a way as to guarantee adequate security of personal data, including protection, by means of appropriate technical and organizational actions, from unauthorized or unlawful processing, loss, destruction and accidental damage

APRE - Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
Via Cavour, 71 - 00184 Roma
Tel.: +39 06 48939993 | email: segreteria@apre.it
Web: www.apre.it
PI/CF: 03929151003
Certificazione ISO 9001

Liaison office Bruxelles
Rue du Trône, 98 - 1050 Bruxelles
Tel.: +32 22902271 | Fax: +32 22177415

What data do we collect?

In the MARINEWIND project APRE collects the following kind of data:

- Personal identification information (i.e. Name, surname, email address, date of birth, gender)

How do we collect your data?

For the newsletter, events, etc. personal data could be collected during the project lifetime, (i.e. through website). Data are collected only from participants who give us the informed consent (GDPR Art. 6.a).

How do we store your data?

APRE establishes how to store the data according to the principle of data protection by design. Therefore, before each project, through a process of risk assessment and if necessary impact assessment, the company defines the most suitable measures to ensure the data protection. Generally, data are securely stored in protected cloud or hard disks placed in locked closet in the company sites. If necessary data are encrypted and when it is possible, they are pseudonymized ((UE 679/2016 art. 4.5). The backup of the data avoids the data loss in the case of hard disk breakage.

Data are generally kept for a period, which is specified on the informed consent. Once the declared period has expired, the data are deleted.

Who has access to data?

The data may be processed only by internal personnel, or data processor duly authorized and instructed to process (GDPR Art.29)

What are the data protection rights? (art. 15-20 GDPR)

The right to access: participants have the right to request APRE for copies of their personal data.

The right to rectification: participants have the right to request that APRE corrects any information they believe is inaccurate. They have also the right to request APRE to complete the incomplete information.

The right to erasure: participants have the right to request that APRE erases their personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to restrict processing: participants have the right to request that APRE restricts processing of personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to object to processing: participants have the right to object to APRE processing of personal data under certain conditions.

The right to data portability: participants have the right to request that APRE transfers the data collected to another organization, or directly to them, under certain conditions.

If participants submit any question, APRE is committed to answer within a month. If they would like to exercise any of these rights, they can contact APRE at: privacy@apre.

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Changes of our privacy policy

APRE keeps its privacy policy under regular review and places any updated on this page. This privacy policy was last updated on 30/06/2020.

How to contact us

If participants have any questions about APRE privacy policy, the data that APRE hold on them, or they would like to exercise one of the data protection rights do not hesitate to contact us.

Email privacy@apre.it

Phone: +39 06 48939993

Address: Via Cavour 71 – 00184 Rome Italy

How to contact the appropriate authority

If any participant feels that APRE has not addressed his concern in a satisfactory manner, he may contact the Italian Data Protection Authority.

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2) SENER

Cerdanyola del Vallès, February 16th, 2023

DECLARATION on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing SENER Ingeniería y Sistemas, S.A., with seat in Av, Zugazarte, 56, Getxo (Bizkaia – Spain), hereby certify that SENER Ingeniería y Sistemas, S.A.:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
- hereby confirm that SENER Ingeniería y Sistemas, S.A., designated a Data Protection Officer: UBT Legal & Compliance - dpo@sener.es.
- hereby confirm that SENER Ingeniería y Sistemas, S.A. as a subsidiary of SENER Grupo de Ingeniería, S.A. has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants.

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Óscar Julià Perich
Director of Innovation and Digitalization

SENER Ingeniería y Sistemas, S.A.

Privacy Policy

Data controller and contact details

Sener Grupo de Ingeniería S.A. (hereinafter, "SENER")

Address: Cervantes, 8 | Getxo, 48930 (Bizkaia) | España

Contact email: info@sener.es

Email of the Sener Group Data Protection Officer: dpd@sener.es

When processing personal data, authorized staff are required to observe the following general principles:

Dignity of the data subject, i.e. the natural person whom the personal data is about

- **Lawfulness, accuracy and transparency:** personal data must be processed in a lawful, accurate and transparent way, in order to guarantee to the data subject adequate security, including protection, through appropriate technical and organizational measures, from unauthorized or unlawful processing and from accidental loss, destruction or damage. With regard to transparency, all information intended for the public or to the data subject must be concise, easily accessible and easily understood; the language used must be simple and clear.
- **Purpose limitation:** the purposes of the processing must be certain, explicit and legitimate, and subsequently processed in a way that is not incompatible with such purposes (without prejudice to further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest or for scientific or historical research purposes; or for statistical purposes).
- **Data minimization:** the data collected must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary with respect to the purposes for which they are processed. Specifically, information systems and computer programs must be configured by minimizing the use of personal data, so as to exclude their processing when the purposes pursued in individual cases can be achieved through anonymous data or other appropriate ways to identify the data subject only in case of necessity ('necessity principle').
- **Accuracy:** the data processed must be accurate and, if necessary, updated, therefore all reasonable steps must be taken to delete or edit inaccurate data in relation to the purposes for which they are processed.
- **Retention limit:** the data processed must be stored in a form that allows identification of the data subject for a period not longer than the necessary to achieve the purposes for which they are collected and processed (unless specific law providing for archiving processing in the public interest or for scientific or historical research purposes, or for statistical purposes).
- **Integrity and confidentiality:** the data must be processed in such a way as to guarantee adequate security of personal data, including protection, by means of appropriate technical and organizational actions, from unauthorized or unlawful processing, loss, destruction and accidental damage.

What data do we collect?

In the MARINEWIND project Sener collects the following kind of data:

- Personal identification information and contact data (i.e. Name, surname, email address, date of birth, gender).

How do we collect your data?

For the newsletter, events, etc. personal data could be collected during the project lifetime, (i.e. through website). Data are collected only from participants who give us the informed consent (GDPR Art. 6.a).

How do we store your data?

Sener establishes how to store the data according to the principle of data protection by design. Therefore, before each project, through a process of risk assessment and if necessary impact assessment, the company defines the most suitable measures to ensure the data protection. Generally, data are securely stored in protected cloud or hard disks placed in locked closet in the company sites. If necessary data are encrypted and when it is possible, they are pseudonymized (GDPR art. 4.5). The backup of the data avoids the data loss in the case of hard disk breakage.

Data are generally kept for a period, which is specified on the informed consent. Once the declared period has expired, the data are deleted.

Who has access to data?

The data may be processed only by internal personnel, or data processor duly authorized and instructed to process (GDPR Art.29).

Rights

At any time, users may exercise the following rights recognised by current data protection regulation:

- **Right of Access:** allows the user to know which information is held, where it has been obtained from, to whom it has been provided and with what uses it has been treated.
- **Right of Rectification:** allows the user to rectify any erroneous or outdated data.
- **Right of Erasure:** allows the user to request that his or her data be no longer processed.
- **Right of Limitation:** allows the user to restrict the processing of their data, but in such a way that they are kept for some subsequent purpose (a legal claim, for example).
- **Right of Portability:** allows the user to obtain a copy of their data in electronic form and, in certain circumstances, to request that they be communicated to another service provider.
- **Right of Opposition:** enables the user to oppose the lawful interest of the SENER Group to request the cessation of the processing of its data.
- **Right to Withdraw Consent,** at any time, for the processing of the personal data, without affecting the lawfulness of the same.

Users may exercise these rights through the following email address protecciondatos@sener.es, stating which right you wish to exercise and providing your ID card or similar document proving your identity.

In case of non-satisfactory response in the exercise of your rights, data subject may ask for further information to our Data Protection Officer, at dpd@sener.es, as well as file a complaint with the Spanish Supervisory Authority, to the following address www.aepd.es.

Modification of the privacy policy

Sener Grupo de Ingeniería reserves its right to modify the present Privacy Policy, always in accordance with the terms permitted by current Spanish legislation and with the corresponding communication to users, by publication in this web page or by any other means of communication or dissemination considered appropriate.

3) Q-PLAN

Thessaloniki, 08/02/2023

DECLARATION

on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, with seat in 11 EL. VENIZELOU ST, KALAMARIA, THESSALONIKI, PC 55133, hereby certify that Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
- hereby confirm that Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL designated a Data Protection Officer: Petros Papadionisiou, papadionisiou@qplan-intl.gr
- hereby confirm that Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants.

Dimitrios A. Daskalakis,
Director & Legal representative

DIMITRIOS
DASKALAKIS

Digitally signed by DIMITRIOS
DASKALAKIS
Date: 2023.02.08 11:54:42 +02'00'

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL Privacy Policy

INTRODUCTION

The management and personnel of Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL (“Company”), are committed to protect your privacy and personal data, in accordance with the requirements of EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The Company has appointed a Data Protection Officer (“DPO”) who assumes the responsibility for addressing any questions regarding this Privacy Policy. For any clarification regarding this privacy policy, including the submission of any request for exercising your rights, please contact our DPO using the following contact details:

CONTACT DETAILS

Company: Q-PLAN International P.C.

DPO’s name: Papadionisiou Petros

DPO’s email: papadionisiou@qplan-intl.gr

Phone number: +30 2310 411191

Street address: 11 El. Venizelou str, 55133, Kalamaria, Thessaloniki, Greece

TYPES OF DATA WE COLLECT

We only collect as many data as necessary to be able to provide you with services that correspond to your needs. These data usually come from you and include:

- **contact details** (name/ surname, email address, street address, mobile phone number, land line phone number),
- **tax details** (name, VAT number, business street address, profession),
- **financial data**, such as: bank accounts, invoices, evidence of tangible assets and financial capacity. These documents are usually required for submitting proposals and managing investment plans and innovation projects under EU and National Funding Programmes.
- **various types of personal data** (e.g. professional information) depending on the specific requirements of the projects that we undertake as these are specified in the relevant contracts with the Funding Authorities (e.g. European Commission).

WHY WE NEED YOUR DATA AND HOW WE USE THEM

We need your data to:

- issue and keep the legal tax documents regarding to the financial transactions between us (contracts, agreements, invoices, etc.);
- receive and make payments;
- comply with legally binding procedures;
- send you bids for our services after a relevant request from your side;
- receive your feedback on problems you may encounter when collaborating with us;
- communicate with you in an effective and swift manner for the purposes of our business relationship;
- submit proposals, monitor the progress of investment plans and manage projects implemented under EU and National Funding Programmes;
- send you newsletters, messages and other promotional material on topics that may interest you such as announcements of new funding Programmes.

We assure you that your data will not be used for purposes other than those mentioned in this policy without your prior notification and consent if required. Our internal processes are implemented in accordance with all confidentiality requirements included in the contracts we sign with our clients (both from the private and the public sector) and with other entities (e.g. European Commission).

CONSENT

We always ask for your consent when we intend to use your personal data for purposes other than those related to the provision of our services such as sending informational emails and newsletters.

You must know that you can always withdraw your consent by communicating with our DPO on the phone (+30 2310 411191) or by email: papadionisiou@qplan-intl.gr. With regards to the promotional messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" at the end of all the relevant messages.

In the event that you provide us with personal information of a third party, you are responsible for informing the person in question of the use of his/ her data and for obtaining his/ her explicit consent that this information is provided for the purposes described above

BASES OF LAWFUL PROCESSING

The lawful bases we apply for processing your personal data are the following:

- i. performance of a contract in which you are a party or activities required for entering into such contract after a relevant request from your side (e.g. submission of a bid);
- ii. compliance with a legal obligation to which we are subject such as tax legislation or public procurement laws;

- iii. your consent when it comes to sending informational emails and newsletters;
- iv. protection of our legitimate interests, especially for purposes of safeguarding the safety of people, materials and facilities under our responsibility.

TRANSFER OF YOUR INFORMATION

We never disclose your information to third parties, except when:

- it is necessary to provide you with a service that you have requested (e.g. to send paper files with a courier service);
- it is required by a critical internal process (e.g. IT support, accounting services, etc.);
- it is imposed by Law (e.g. Tax Authorities).

Specifically, our Company discloses your personal data to the following types of recipients:

- State authorities and law enforcement agencies, when this is required for the fulfillment of a legally or administratively defined obligation or the performance of an audit (e.g. from tax authorities) and in accordance with the relevant legal procedures.
- Business partners (e.g. subcontractors, banks, accounting services, courier services, etc.).

When your data is transferred to the above third parties, we seek to minimize this data to the extent necessary to achieve the specific purpose. Unless otherwise prohibited by a legal procedure, our partners are obligated and contractually bound to protect your personal data in accordance with our policy and to comply with applicable privacy and data protection laws and regulations.

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL maintains a copy of its contacts list on the MailChimp platform (<http://mailchimp.com>), which is used to send bulk informational emails. The personal data contained in this contacts list is managed and protected under Article 12 of MailChimp's Privacy Policy.

RETENTION AND ERASURE OF YOUR PERSONAL DATA

We will retain your personal data for as long as it is required to fulfil the purposes outlined in this Privacy Policy unless a longer retention period is imposed by law. The criteria used to determine the retention period include:

- The time length of our business relationship.
- Relevant legal and contractual obligations to which we are subject (for example, tax laws require us to keep records of your transactions for a certain period, EU funded projects require us to keep records that may include personal data for certain periods).
- Safeguarding our Company from potential legal and business complications such as dispute resolution, complaint handling, fraud prevention and other illegal activities.

After the end of retention period, your personal data are destroyed, deleted or anonymized.

4) WAVEC

Lisbon, 17 February 2023

DECLARATION on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing WavEC Offshore Renewables, with seat in Edifício Diogo Cão, Doca de Alcântara Norte, 1350-352 Lisbon, Portugal, hereby certify that WavEC Offshore Renewables:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR).
- hereby confirm that WavEC Offshore Renewables does not designate a Data Protection Officer because none of the criteria in Art. 37 sub. 1 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are met in the case of Offshore Renewables. Nevertheless, Offshore Renewables has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants.

Marco Alves
WavEC CEO

WavEC Data Privacy Policy

Policy statement

WavEC is committed to complying with its responsibilities under EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

WavEC has defined and formalized an internal process for correct processing of personal data. When processing personal data, authorized staff are required to observe the following general principles:

Types of data we collect and how we use them

We only collect the necessary to be able to provide you with services that correspond to your needs. These data usually come from you and include:

- **contact details** (name, address, phone numbers),
- **tax details** (name, VAT number, business street address),
- **financial data** (e.g. bank accounts, invoices),
- **various types of personal data** (depending on the specific requirements of funding projects that we undertake as these are specified in the relevant contracts with the Funding Authorities).

Why do we need your data and how do we use them

We need your data to:

- issue and keep the legal tax documents regarding to the financial transactions between us (contracts, agreements, invoices, etc.);
- receive and make payments;
- comply with legally binding procedures;
- submit proposals and manage projects implemented under EU and National Funding Programmes;
- send you newsletters, messages and other promotional material (e.g. press releases) on topics that may interest.

We assure you that your data will not be used for purposes other than those mentioned in this policy without your prior notification and consent if required. Our internal processes are implemented in accordance with all confidentiality requirements included in the contracts we sign with our clients and with other entities (e.g. European Commission).

We always ask for your consent when we intend to use your personal data for purposes other than those related to the provision of our services such as sending informational emails and newsletters.

How do we store your data

WavEC establishes how to store the data according to the principle of data protection. Generally, data are securely stored in protected cloud or hard disks placed in locked closet in the company sites. If necessary, data are encrypted. The backup of the data avoids the data loss in the case of hard disk breakage.

Data are generally kept for a period, which is specified on the informed consent. Once the declared period has expired, the data are deleted.

Who has access to data

The data may be processed only by internal personnel, or data processor duly authorized and instructed to process (GDPR Art.29).

Right of interested parties

With reference to the processing of personal data, the interested party has the right to:

- access their data, check it and ask for it to be updated or corrected;
- withdraw, at any time, the consent to the processing of their personal data previously expressed;
- oppose the processing of their data if this occurs on a legal basis other than the previously expressed consent, including the processing of data for commercial, marketing and profiling purposes;
- request the limitation of the processing of their data. In this case the owner will not process the data for any other purpose than their conservation;
- obtain the cancellation or removal of their personal data, if the conditions set out in article 17 of the GDPR are met. The right to cancellation does not exist, pursuant to art. 17, paragraph 3, letter d of the GDPR, for data whose processing is necessary for scientific research purposes if it risks making it impossible and/or seriously compromising the objectives of the research itself;
- receive their data in a structured format, commonly used and readable by an automatic device and, where technically feasible, to have them transferred to another owner;
- oppose automated processing and not be subjected to processing based solely on automated decisions including profiling;
- propose a complaint to the competent personal data protection supervisory authority or take legal action.

To exercise one or more of these rights, interested parties can direct a request to the contact details of the owner indicated in this document.

How to contact us

If participants have any questions about WavEC *Data Privacy Policy*, the data that WavEC hold on them, or they would like to exercise one of the data protection rights, do not hesitate to contact us:

E-mail: janete.goncalves@wavec.org

5) CNR

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
ISTITUTO DI INGEGNERIA DEL MARE

DECLARATION

on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing INM CNR (The Institute of Marine Engineering - National Research Council), with seat in ROME – Via di Vallerano, 139 hereby certify that INM CNR :

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
- hereby confirm that CNR (National Research Council) designated a Data Protection Officer: Dr. Raffaele Conte e-mail: rpdc@cnr.it; pec: rpdc@pec.cnr.it. The DPO contact point for feedback from the interested parties, is the Director of Institute of Marine Engineering (in short INM) Eng. Alessandro Iafrati, who can be contacted at the following address:
 Pec: protocollo.inm@pec.cnr.it
 e-mail: alessandro.iafrati@cnr.it
 Tel Secretariat INM +39 0650299222
- hereby confirm that INM CNR has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants.

THE DIRECTOR

Eng. Alessandro Iafrati

Alessandro
 Iafrati
 09.02.2023
 15:44:58
 GMT+01:00

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
ISTITUTO DI INGEGNERIA DEL MARE

PRIVACY NOTICE ON THE PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

Information pursuant to art. 13 of EU Regulation 2016/679

As required by the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR 2016/679, Article 13) and by the Legislative Decree 2003/196 "Codice della Privacy" and subsequent amendments, we inform you that personal data, conferred to Institute of Marine Engineering (in short INM CNR) of National Research Council, are processed, both in paper and electronic form, for the purposes indicated below.

Data Controller and Data Protection Officer

The Data Controller is Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Piazzale Aldo Moro, 7 - 00185 Roma, Italy.

The contact point for the exercise of the data subject's rights is the Director of the Institute of Marine Engineering INM CNR, Via di Vallerano, 139 – 00128 Rome, Italy;

email address: direttore.inm@inm.cnr.it

Pec : protocollo.inm@cnr.it

Tel. n. +39 0650299222

The Privacy Officer of the Institute of Marine Engineering INM CNR can be contacted at the email address:

Email address: monica.zirondelli@cnr.it

The CNR Data Protection Officer (also known as DPO (Data Protection Officer) or RPD, (Responsabile della Protezione dei Dati) can be reached at the email addresses: dpo@cnr.it ; PEC (Electronic Certified Mail): rpd@pec.cnr.it

Persons authorized to process data

The personal data are processed by internal personnel previously authorized and designated as 'persons authorized to process', who are given appropriate instructions regarding measures, precautions and modus operandi.

Purpose and legal basis of the processing

The processing of personal data is carried out in compliance with the current legislation on privacy, therefore INM CNR undertakes to treat the data according to the principles of correctness, lawfulness and transparency, in compliance with the purposes indicated below, collecting them to the extent necessary and exact for processing, having them treated only by specifically authorized personnel.

Personal data will be processed for institutional purposes, as part of activities strictly connected or instrumental to the administrative and accounting management of the existing relationship with INM CNR and necessary to fulfil the following requirements:

- legal obligations, including obligations regarding administrative transparency;
- obligations under Community legislation;
- contractual obligations deriving from relations with other public and private entities;
- obligations established by sector legislations and regulations;
- instructions given by authorities legitimated to do so by supervisory and control bodies.
- Ethical rules for processing for statistical or scientific research purposes pursuant to article 20, paragraph 4, of Legislative Decree 10/08/2018, n.101-19 December 2018
- Behaviour Code of Public Workers

Therefore, in the existence of the conditions of lawfulness of the processing, pursuant to art. 6 paragraph 1 letters b, c, and of EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), the consent of the interested party is not required.

Any additional purposes (e.g. scientific dissemination purposes related to the publication of photos or audio/video recordings), supported by suitable legal basis or an explicit and justified request and by specific and optional consent, will be the object of a specific privacy notice.

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
ISTITUTO DI INGEGNERIA DEL MARE

Methods of treatment and retention time

The processing takes place with tools suitable to guarantee the security and confidentiality of the data, in compliance with the provisions of Chapter II (Principles) and Chapter IV (Controller and processor) of the GDPR.

The processing of personal data is carried out by means of the operations indicated in art. 4 of the Codice della Privacy and art. 4 n. 2 of the GDPR and more precisely: collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction. The processing is carried out with manual and / or IT and telematics tools, with organization and processing logics strictly related to the purposes themselves and in any case in such a way as to guarantee the security, integrity and confidentiality of the data in compliance with the organizational, physical and logical measures required by the legislation in force.

Data will be processed for the entire period in which the relationship established with the interested party elapses and, after the termination, for the eventual fulfilment of legal obligations in accordance with the regulations in force on the conservation of administrative documents.

Transfer of data abroad

Always within the limits relevant to the aforementioned purposes, the processed data may also be transferred abroad, to countries of the European Union and to non-EU countries or international organizations, for which there are adequacy decisions of the European Commission, or on the basis of adequate guarantees provided by the Country to which the data must be transferred.

In case of transfer, the interested party has the right to obtain information regarding the legal basis for the transfer of personal data outside the European Union or to an organization, international or consisting of two or more countries, governed by public international laws, as well as about the security measures adopted by the owner to protect the Data.

Data communication

Without express consent (pursuant to Article 24 letter a, b, d of the "Codice della Privacy" and Article 6 letter b, c, d of the GDPR), the Data Controller may communicate the data processed for the purposes described above to: Supervisory bodies, Judicial authorities as well as to all other subjects to whom communication is mandatory by law for the accomplishment of the aforementioned purposes. Data will not be disclosed.

Furthermore, for the pursuit of contractual obligations with funding bodies, the staff of the Institute's administrative offices may request to provide documentation necessary for the reporting of research activities financed on external funds in which the interested party is involved, in addition to that already provided to the Entity on the basis of specific provisions issued by the Entity itself.

The personnel authorized for the administrative and accounting management of these documents guarantees the maximum confidentiality of the data and information acquired.

The provision of data is mandatory and necessary for the fulfilment of the institutional purposes and legal obligations mentioned above. Any refusal to provide the aforementioned data and documents makes it impossible to carry out any reporting operations on research activities on external funds.

Right of interested parties

With reference to the processing of personal data, the interested party has the right to:

- access their data, check it and ask for it to be updated or corrected;
- withdraw, at any time, the consent to the processing of their personal data previously expressed;
- oppose the processing of their data if this occurs on a legal basis other than the previously expressed consent, including the processing of data for commercial, marketing and profiling purposes;
- request the limitation of the processing of their data. In this case the owner will not process the data for any other purpose than their conservation;
- obtain the cancellation or removal of their personal data, if the conditions set out in article 17 of the GDPR are met. The right to cancellation does not exist, pursuant to art. 17, paragraph 3, letter d of the GDPR, for data whose processing is necessary for scientific research purposes if it risks making it impossible and/or seriously

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
ISTITUTO DI INGEGNERIA DEL MARE

compromising the objectives of the research itself;

- receive their data in a structured format, commonly used and readable by an automatic device and, where technically feasible, to have them transferred to another owner;
- oppose automated processing and not be subjected to processing based solely on automated decisions including profiling;
- propose a complaint to the competent personal data protection supervisory authority or take legal action.

To exercise one or more of these rights, interested parties can direct a request to the contact details of the owner indicated in this document.

6) RSE

Milano, 07/02/2023

DECLARATION on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing **RSE S.p.A.**, with seat in Milan, Via Rubattino 54, Italy, hereby certify that RSE:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013.
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
- hereby confirm that RSE designated a Data Protection Officer: Elisabetta Vicini (privacy@rse-web.it, rse@legalmail.it).
- hereby confirm that RSE has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants.

Firmato digitalmente da:
MAURIZIO DELFANTI

.....
RSE S.p.A.
Chief Executive Officer
Prof. Maurizio Delfanti

RSE Privacy Policy

Data controller

Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico – RSE S.p.A., Via Raffaele Rubattino n. 54, Milan, Italy, rse@legalmail.it.

RSE's processing of personal data takes place in compliance with the GDPR, with the Italian Legislative Decree no. 196/03 ("Personal Data Protection Code") and with European Data Protection Board (EDPB) guidelines, as well as with the principles of lawfulness, correctness and transparency, adequacy and relevance.

The data may be processed only by internal personnel duly authorized and instructed to process (GDPR Article 29). Occasionally, personal data may be processed by a data processor appointed to properly follow the instructions given through a specific Data Protection Agreement (GDPR Article 28).

RSE adopts the following appropriate technical and organizational measures to prevent unauthorized or unlawful processing, loss, destruction, alteration, access and accidental damage to personal data:

- identification of a person with day-to-day responsibility for information security within the organization;
- periodic checks to ensure that security measures remain appropriate and up to date;
- co-ordination between key people in the organization;
- system, data and devices security (e.g. access controls, back-up policies, use of VPN, encryption, etc.);
- implementation of the data breach internal procedure;
- maintenance and regular updating of a record of processing activities (GDPR Article 30).

Prior to any personal data processing RSE provides the data subjects with specific information (GDPR Article 13) regarding the identity and the contact details of the controller, the contact details of the data protection officer, the purposes of the processing for which the personal data are intended as well as the legal basis, etc.

The data subject's rights (GDPR Articles 15-22) may be exercised contacting RSE'S DPO or the internal Data Protection Working Group via the following e-mail addresses: privacy@rse-web.it, rse@legalmail.it.

Personal data collected

In the MARINEWIND project RSE collects the following kind of data: Personal identification information (i.e. Name, surname, email address, date of birth, gender).

Means of collection

Personal data could be collected during the project lifetime, (i.e. through website). Data are collected only from subjects who give us the informed consent (GDPR Article 6.a).

Data storage

RSE is engaged in system, data and devices security (e.g. through access controls, back-up policies, use of VPN, encryption) aiming to ensure data protection. Generally, data are securely stored in protected cloud or hard disks placed in locked closet in the company premises. The backup of the data avoids the data loss in the case of hard disk breakage.

Data are generally kept for a period, which is specified on the information provided to data subjects. Once the declared period has expired, the data are deleted.

Access to data

The data may be processed only by internal personnel, or data processor duly authorized and instructed to process (GDPR Article 29)

Data protection rights (art. 15-22 GDPR)

The right to access: participants have the right to request RSE for copies of their personal data.

The right to rectification: participants have the right to request that RSE corrects any information they believe is inaccurate. They have also the right to request RSE to complete the incomplete information.

The right to erasure: participants have the right to request that RSE erases their personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to restrict processing: participants have the right to request that RSE restricts processing of personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to object to processing: participants have the right to object to RSE processing of personal data under certain conditions.

The right to data portability: participants have the right to request that RSE transfers the data collected to another organization, or directly to them, under certain conditions.

If participants submit any question, RSE is committed to answer within a month. If they would like to exercise any of these rights, they can contact RSE at: privacy@rse-web.it.

RSE's contacts

If participants have any questions about RSE privacy policy, the data that RSE hold on them, or they would like to exercise one of the data protection rights do not hesitate to contact us.

- Email: privacy@rse-web.it

- Phone: +39 023992.1
- Address: Via Raffaele Rubattino n. 54, Milan, 20134, Italy

Data protection authority

If any participant feels that RSE has not addressed their concern in a satisfactory manner, they may contact the Italian Data Protection Authority.

7) EP

ASSOCIATION OF NATIONAL ORGANISATIONS
OF FISHING ENTERPRISES IN THE EU

Brussels, 21 February 2023

DECLARATION on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing Europêche, with seat in Rue Montoyer 24, Brussels hereby certify that Europêche:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR).
- hereby confirm that Europêche does not designate a Data Protection Officer because none of the criteria in Art. 37 sub. 1 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are met in the case of Europêche. Nevertheless, Europêche has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants.

Daniel Voces de Onáindi González
Managing Director
Europêche

EUROPÊCHE
Rue Montoyer 24
B - 1000 Bruxelles
+32.2.230.48.48
www.europeche.org

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be "DVG", is written over the printed name and title of the Managing Director.

ASSOCIATION OF NATIONAL ORGANISATIONS
OF FISHING ENTERPRISES IN THE EU

Europêche Privacy Policy

In compliance with the GDPR and on the basis of its organization chart, Europêche has defined and formalized an Organizational Model of privacy related liability aimed at the correct processing of personal data.

When processing personal data, the staff are required to observe the following general principles:

Dignity of the data subject, i.e. the natural person whom the personal data is about

- *Lawfulness, accuracy and transparency:* personal data must be processed in a lawful, accurate and transparent way, in order to guarantee to the data subject adequate security, including protection, through appropriate technical and organizational measures, from unauthorized or unlawful processing and from accidental loss, destruction or damage. With regard to transparency, all information intended for the public or to the data subject must be concise, easily accessible and easily understood; the language used must be simple and clear.
- *Purpose limitation:* the purposes of the processing must be certain, explicit and legitimate, and subsequently processed in a way that is not incompatible with such purposes (without prejudice to further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest or for scientific or historical research purposes; or for statistical purposes).
- *Data minimization:* the data collected must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary with respect to the purposes for which they are processed. Specifically, information systems and computer programs must be configured by minimizing the use of personal data, so as to exclude their processing when the purposes pursued in individual cases can be achieved through anonymous data or other appropriate ways to identify the data subject only in case of necessity ('necessity principle').
- *Accuracy:* the data processed must be accurate and, if necessary, updated, therefore all reasonable steps must be taken to delete or edit inaccurate data in relation to the purposes for which they are processed.
- *Retention limit:* the data processed must be stored in a form that allows identification of the data subject for a period not longer than the necessary to achieve the purposes for which they are collected and processed (unless specific law providing for archiving processing in the public interest or for scientific or historical research purposes, or for statistical purposes).
- *Integrity and confidentiality:* the data must be processed in such a way as to guarantee adequate security of personal data, including protection, by means of appropriate technical and organizational actions, from unauthorized or unlawful processing, loss, destruction and accidental damage

ASSOCIATION OF NATIONAL ORGANISATIONS
OF FISHING ENTERPRISES IN THE EU

What data may be collected?

In the MARINEWIND project Europêche may collect the following kind of data:

- Personal identification information (i.e. Name, surname, email address, date of birth, gender)

How do we collect your data?

Data are collected only from participants who give us the informed consent (GDPR Art. 6.a).

Who has access to data?

The data may be processed only by internal personnel, or data processor duly authorized and instructed to process (GDPR Art.29)

What are the data protection rights? (art. 15-20 GDPR)

The right to access: participants have the right to request Europêche for copies of their personal data.

The right to rectification: participants have the right to request that Europêche corrects any information they believe is inaccurate. They have also the right to request Europêche to complete the incomplete information.

The right to erasure: participants have the right to request that Europêche erases their personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to restrict processing: participants have the right to request that Europêche restricts processing of personal data, under certain conditions.

The right to object to processing: participants have the right to object to Europêche processing of personal data under certain conditions.

The right to data portability: participants have the right to request that Europêche transfers the data collected to another organization, or directly to them, under certain conditions.

If participants submit any question, Europêche is committed to answer within a month. If they would like to exercise any of these rights, they can contact Europêche at: info@europêche.org

How to contact us

If participants have any questions about Europêche privacy policy, the data that Europêche hold on them, or they would like to exercise one of the data protection rights do not hesitate to contact us.

Email info@europêche.org

Phone: +32 2 230 48 48

Address: Rue Montoyer 24, 1000, Brussels BELGIUM

8) UoY

DocuSign Envelope ID: 406AC4E7-3129-463F-AFDE-F478024A932A

Research Grants & Contracts
University of York
York YO10 5DD
20th February 2022

DECLARATION

on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing University of York, with seat in Heslington, York, hereby certify that University of York:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to the Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
- hereby confirm that University of York designated a Data Protection Officer: Emma Montgomery emma.montgomery@york.ac.uk.
- hereby confirm that University of York has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants.

DocuSigned by:
Emma Montgomery
.....RF2823A8ED8E8.....

Emma Montgomery
Head of Research Grants Operations

University of York Privacy Policy

Drafting GDPR compliant privacy notices

Whenever the University of York gathers or receives [personal](#) or [special category data](#), it should provide a privacy notice to the [data subject](#). This is not a new requirement under data protection legislation. However, the GDPR does introduce more granular requirements for notices. For a full breakdown of all required elements see [GDPR Compliant Privacy Notice Checklist \(MS Word 16kb\)](#).

In order to ensure consistency across the University, a template privacy notice has been produced to provide standard wording for those elements that will be generic to all University activities. The template can be accessed [here](#). Individual departments will, however, need to ensure local notices explain:

1. why data is being gathered;
2. what legal basis is being relied on to process data;
3. whether data will be shared with a third party and, if so, why.

In terms of a worked example;

Privacy Notice

The information provided on this form will be used by the Information Governance Office to ...

You will need to provide a clear description of purpose here e.g. consider your application and, if successful, enrol you to the programme; send you regular newsletter updates about information compliance; better understand your experience of studying at a distance and allow us to identify ways to improve provisions for distance learners.

Data will be processed because ...

You will need to explain the legal basis for processing here e.g. you have given us your consent; it is necessary for the performance of a contract with you; we have a legal obligation to do so.

For a full list of grounds see [here](#).

Data will be shared with ... for the following purposes ...

Insert a list of all external bodies, agencies, service providers etc. that you will share the data with and/or list all internal departments that will use the data for distinct purposes. Ensure the rationale for sharing is clearly articulated.

Data will be transferred ...

You will need to explain whether data will be transferred internationally here, i.e. outside of the European Economic Area e.g. to the United States under Privacy Shield; to Australia using

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Model Contract Clauses. As a general rule, get in touch with dataprotection@york.ac.uk if you intend to transfer data internationally.

You will also need to tell individuals whether their data will be subject to automated decision making (including profiling) and, if so, advise how decisions will be made. You should also tell them about the significance and consequence of any automated decision.

For the remainder of this privacy notice see, [General Privacy Notice](#).

If you are unsure how to determine the legal basis for processing, please contact dataprotection@york.ac.uk for advice.

9) ESC

Thursday, 09th February 2023, United Kingdom

DECLARATION on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection

I, the undersigned, representing Energy Systems Catapult, with seat in Cannon House (7th Floor), Priory Queensway, Birmingham, United Kingdom, hereby certify that Energy Systems Catapult:

- applies **ethical principles and guidelines** of the Horizon Europe programme according to Article 19 of the Regulation (EU) [2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013,
- applies data protection rules according to Regulation (EU) [2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR).
- hereby confirm that Energy Systems Catapult does not designate a Data Protection Officer because none of the criteria in Art. 37 sub. 1 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is met in the case of Energy Systems Catapult. Nevertheless, Energy Systems Catapult has in place an internal regulation for personal data management and protection and related data privacy policy (see below) to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects/research participants and included a privacy working group in its organization chart coordinated by the Legal team (dataprotectionoffice@es.catapult.org.uk)

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Paul Jordan", is written over a light blue horizontal line.

.....
Paul Jordan

Business Leader, Innovator Support & International

.....
This document is marked as confidential

Energy Systems Catapult Data Protection Policy

(Extract from ESC Data Protection Policy)

Policy statement

Energy Systems Catapult is committed to complying with its responsibilities under UK data protection legislation and, where appropriate, to identify and follow best practice.

Roles and Responsibilities

The Executive Committee, reporting to the Board, has overall accountability for data protection compliance and is responsible for reviewing and approving this policy.

The Catapult Data Protection Owner (Chief Finance Officer) is responsible for:

1. Providing strategic direction to support a culture of compliance;
2. Allocating appropriate resources to enable compliance with this policy and ensure that risks are managed appropriately;
3. Authorising the response to a security breach, complaint or investigation and assessing the impact on the Catapult and its business activities; Page 2 of 5
4. Ensuring that appropriate action is taken against those who breach this policy; and
5. Reporting to the Board.

The Data Protection Solicitor is the solicitor in Energy Systems Catapult's legal team responsible for:

1. Monitoring data protection compliance, including carrying out compliance checks or audits;
2. Producing and implementing data protection policies and procedures;
3. Investigating any suspected breaches and managing the response to an identified breach;
4. Providing compliance reports to the Catapult Data Protection Owner, Audit and Risk Committee and Board; 5. Providing advice and guidance on data protection matters to project teams and others within the Catapult; 6. Approving consent forms;
5. Reviewing data protection protocols from service providers;
6. Proposing and coordinating data protection training and awareness programmes as appropriate;
7. Assessing the impact of changes in data protection legislation;
8. Ensuring that any requests or complaints from individuals are dealt with promptly and appropriately;

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9. Responding to enquiries, assessments and other correspondence from the Information Commissioner's Office; and
10. Reporting to the chair of the Audit and Risk Committee and the Board.

Data controller and data processor

A data controller has decision making rights in respect of personal information and determines what information is collected and how it is processed. A data processor handles personal information on behalf of a data controller. A data processor is not permitted to use the information for any purpose other than as instructed by the data controller. The Catapult can find itself acting as controller or processor, or in certain circumstances, as both controller and processor.

Collaborative and Research Projects

If working on a project that might use or store personal information, the Catapult will work with its project collaborators so that, where possible and considering the goals of the project:

1. the project uses anonymous or depersonalised information; or
2. only anonymised or depersonalised information is shared with the Catapult.

The Catapult will require that consent is obtained from any individual participating in a Catapult project for the collection, use and storage of their personal information. As such, the Catapult will ensure that individuals who take part in Catapult projects (e.g. trialists) are provided with appropriate information about the way in which their personal information will be used by the Catapult (and, where relevant, by third party organisations) and with appropriate choices regarding the collection, use and disclosure of that information.

Research data is information relevant to, or of interest to researchers, either as inputs into or outputs from research, such as materials resulting from primary data collection or generation, or derived from existing sources and intended to be analysed in the course of a research project. The same principles will apply to research data as for collaborative projects.

Most major research funders have guidelines or requirements about use, sharing and retention of academic research data during and after a research project; the Catapult will need to consider these as part of its data protection impact assessment and make enquiries for each project it identifies as possibly being subject to any third party requirements; and then observe any such requirements. The Catapult should also consider whether there will be any academic publication of research data and if so, whether the publisher has any requirements about the use, sharing and retention of such data.

The Catapult will need to complete a DPIA for any collaborative and/or research project that might use or store personal information. It will be at the Catapult's discretion if we should be the owners of the DPIA or if the Catapult allows its collaborative partners to undertake the assessment. The responsibility will depend upon who is the data controller. Where both parties are data controllers the Catapult should produce its own DPIA. Page 4 of 5.

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To ensure that we prevent unauthorised access, disclosure, destruction and amendments of personal and/or research data, the Catapult requires the employees to restrict access to the data, to store it in a safe place and not store highly sensitive data on a cloud based server. All employees are responsible for storing the data safely and destroying the data if there is no longer a requirement for it.

Accuracy and Relevance

We will ensure that any personal data we process is accurate, adequate, relevant and not excessive, given the purpose for which it was obtained. We will not process personal data obtained for one purpose for any unconnected purpose unless the individual concerned has agreed to this or would otherwise reasonably expect this.

Individuals may ask that we correct inaccurate personal data relating to them. If someone believes that information about them is inaccurate, they should inform the Data Protection Solicitor. Employees must take reasonable steps to ensure that personal data the Catapult hold about them is accurate and updated as required.

Subject Access Requests

Under data protection legislation, individuals are entitled, subject to certain exceptions, to request access to information held about them. If a member of staff receives a subject access request, they should refer that request immediately to the Data Protection Solicitor. Information is to be provided free of charge to the requestor within one month therefore, it is imperative that the request is passed on as soon as possible. The Data Protection Solicitor may ask you to help us comply with requests. Members of staff should contact the Data Protection Solicitor if they would like to request information held about them.

Reporting Breaches

All members of staff have an obligation to report actual or potential data protection compliance failures. This allows the Catapult to:

- investigate the breach and take remedial steps if necessary;
- maintain a register of breaches; and
- notify the Information Commissioner's Office if necessary.

Working with Other Organisations

The Catapult may work with a variety of other organisations in circumstances where personal information may be collected, transferred, held or maintained. Such other organisations may include consultants, project collaborators, purchasers or suppliers of data, and those providing IT or consultancy services to the Catapult. Where these third parties will receive, supply or process any personal information, the Catapult will ensure that appropriate contracts are put in place defining the data protection roles and responsibilities of the respective parties.

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Consequences of Non-Compliance

Failure to comply with the data protection responsibilities described in this policy may result in enforcement action or financial penalties being imposed on the Catapult by the Information Commissioner's Office, claims for compensation by individuals affected by a breach and/or damage to the reputation of the Catapult. It may also result in criminal liability for the Catapult and, in certain circumstances, for individual members of staff. As a result, a failure to comply with this policy is considered a serious disciplinary matter which could result in disciplinary action, including dismissal or contract termination.

How to contact us

If participants have any questions about Energy Systems Catapult Data Protection Policy, the data that ESC hold on them, or they would like to exercise one of the data protection rights, do not hesitate to contact us.

Email dataprotectionoffice@es.catapult.org.uk

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APPENDIX 2 – DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS

Beneficiary and Associated Partner Name	Country	DPO Name and Surname	DPO Contact details
Agency for the promotion of European Research	Italy	N/A ⁵	N/A
Sener ingenieria y sistemas SA	Spain	N/A	dpo@sener.es
Q-Plan International Advisors PC	Greece	Petros Papadionisiou	Papadionisiou@qplan-intl.gr
WavEC Offshore Renewables – Centro de Energia Offshore Associação	Portugal	N/A	N/A
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Italy	Raffaele Conte	dpo@cnr.it
Ricerca sul Sistema energetico – RSE SPA	Italy	Elisabetta Vicini	privacy@rse-web.it ; rse@legalname.it
Association des organisations nationales d'entreprises de pêche de l'ue	Belgium	N/A	N/A
University of York	United Kingdom	Emma Montgomery	emma.montgomery@york.ac.uk
Energy Systems Catapult Limited	United Kingdom	N/A ⁶	dataprotectionoffice@es.catapult.org.uk

⁵ None of the criteria in Art. 37 sub. 1 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are met in the case of APRE

⁶ No designated DPO, but the legal oversees all GDPR, DP and other compliances

APPENDIX 3 – INFORMED CONSENT USED FOR EVENTS PARTICIPATION

1) ENGLISH LANGUAGE VERSION

I hereby authorize Beneficiaries of the Horizon Europe MARINEWIND project (Grant Agreement No. 101075572) to collect, process and store information about my name, surname, affiliation and contact information (email, telephone number) for up to two years after the project ends for the purpose of project implementation, specifically for recording information about my registration and participation in project meetings and events (workshops, webinars, etc.), in paper and digital form.

I also authorize Beneficiaries of the Horizon Europe MARINEWIND project to take pictures of me and to record my image in the form of a video in each location where project meetings or project activities take place, including online events (subject to the project’s confidentiality and security rules set out in the Grant Agreement), during the whole duration of the project to be used for the reporting and promotional purposes of the project and affiliated activities. With respect to this, these pictures and videos can be recorded, stored, processed, reproduced, exhibited and publicly published by any member of the MARINEWIND consortium as well as any third party contracted to produce the promotional material of the project, using any kind of media (including paper, computer, audio-visual, etc.), up to two years after the project ends.

The information provided by me during the project event (e.g. professional opinions) can only be used for research purposes related to the project implementation

The information provided by me as well as my image will not be transferred to any third party nor processed in a manner inconsistent with the purposes for which they have been initially collected, without prejudice to any applicable legal provision of any kind.

I acknowledge that I received all the required information about the data processing. I confirm that I am aware of my right to access any personal data related to me, the right to modify or rectify these data, cancel as well as object to the use of data and to ask for restriction of processing these data. I can also withdraw my consent for the future use at any time without any justification.

To exercise the above-mentioned rights, please send a written request to (email address of the beneficiary and Associated Partner’s organizing the activity).

ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Please select your choice below

Clicking on the ‘Agree’ button indicates that

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>You have read the above-mentioned information</i> • <i>You are clearly informed about your data protection rights</i> 	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Agree to the processing of my personal data for the purpose of event participation</i>
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<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>You voluntarily agree to participate in the event</i>• <i>You are at least 18 years of age</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Agree to the use of my image (video and photos) for MARINEWIND reporting and promotional purposes</i>
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2) ITALIAN LANGUAGE VERSION

Autorizzo i beneficiari del progetto Horizon Europe MARINEWIND (Grant Agreement numero 101075572) a raccogliere, trattare ed archiviare i miei dati personali, quali nome, cognome, ente di appartenenza e contatti personali (email, numero di telefono) fino a due anni dopo la fine del progetto, ai fini della realizzazione delle attività progettuali, e, nello specifico, per tener traccia in formato cartaceo o digitale del mio interesse e della mia partecipazione agli eventi di progetto (meetings, workshops, webinars, etc).

Inoltre, autorizzo i beneficiari del progetto Horizon Europe MARINEWIND all'utilizzo della mia immagine, nella forma di fotografie o video, in caso di eventi di progetto, inclusi gli eventi online (nel rispetto delle regole di confidenzialità e sicurezza descritte nel Grant Agreement), per tutta la durata del progetto, e al loro utilizzo sia per la reportistica che per le attività di promozione del progetto e delle attività ad esso correlate. A questo specifico proposito, fotografie e video possono essere raccolti, archiviati, trattati, riprodotti, esposti e pubblicati da ogni membro del consorzio MARINEWIND e da ogni terza parte legata da contratto per la realizzazione di materiale promozionale per il progetto su diversi media (inclusi carta stampata, computer, audio-visivo, etc.) fino a due anni dopo la fine del progetto.

Ogni informazione da me fornita durante l'attività di progetto (per esempio, opinioni professionali) potrà essere utilizzata solo con finalità di ricerca nelle fasi di realizzazione del progetto.

Ogni informazione da me fornita, così come la mia immagine, non potrà essere trasferita a parti terze né trattata in disaccordo con le finalità con cui i dati sono stati inizialmente raccolti, senza ostare all'applicazione di alcuna disposizione legale.

Confermo di aver ricevuto tutte le informazioni richieste rispetto al trattamento dei dati. Confermo di essere consapevole dei miei diritti di avere accesso a tutti i miei dati personali, di modificare o correggere tali dati, chiederne la cancellazione o oppormi all'utilizzo degli stessi e di potere esercitare il diritto chiedere restrizioni al loro trattamento. Posso esercitare il diritto di ritirare il mio consenso al futuro utilizzo dei dati in qualsiasi momento senza che sia richiesta alcuna giustificazione.

Per esercitare i diritti descritti sopra, è possibile mandare una richiesta scritta all'indirizzo (indirizzo e-mail dell'organizzatore di ciascuna attività).

CONSENSO ELETTRONICO

Selezionare una delle seguenti opzioni.

L'opzione 'Acconsento' indica che:

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ha letto le informazioni fornite sopra</i> • <i>Ha ricevuto informazioni chiare riguardo i suoi diritti di protezione dei dati</i> | |
|--|--|

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Acconsente volontariamente a partecipare all'evento</i>• <i>Ha almeno 18 anni</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> <i>Acconsento al trattamento dei miei dati personali ai fini della partecipazione all'evento</i><input type="checkbox"/> <i>Acconsento all'utilizzo della mia immagine (video e fotografie) per la reportistica e le attività promozionali di MARINEWIND</i>
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3) SPANISH LANGUAGE VERSION

Por la presente autorizo a los Beneficiarios del proyecto Horizon Europe MARINEWIND (Convenio de subvención nº 101075572) a recopilar, procesar y almacenar información sobre mi nombre, apellidos, afiliación e información de contacto (correo electrónico, número de teléfono) durante un máximo de dos años después de la finalización del proyecto a efectos de la ejecución del mismo, concretamente para registrar información sobre mi inscripción y participación en reuniones y eventos del proyecto (talleres, seminarios web, etc.), en papel y en formato digital.

Asimismo, autorizo a los beneficiarios del proyecto Horizonte Europa MARINEWIND a que tomen fotografías mías y graben mi imagen en forma de vídeo en cada lugar en el que se celebren reuniones o actividades del proyecto, incluidos los eventos en línea (con sujeción a las normas de confidencialidad y seguridad del proyecto establecidas en el Acuerdo de subvención), durante toda la duración del proyecto, para que se utilicen con fines informativos y promocionales del proyecto y de las actividades afiliadas. Con respecto a ello, estas imágenes y vídeos podrán ser grabados, almacenados, procesados, reproducidos, exhibidos y publicados públicamente por cualquier miembro del consorcio MARINEWIND, así como por cualquier tercero contratado para producir el material promocional del proyecto, utilizando cualquier tipo de medio (incluyendo papel, ordenador, audiovisual, etc.), hasta dos años después de la finalización del proyecto.

La información facilitada por mí durante el evento del proyecto (por ejemplo, opiniones profesionales) sólo podrá utilizarse con fines de investigación relacionados con la ejecución del proyecto.

Los datos facilitados por mí, así como mi imagen, no serán cedidos a terceros ni tratados de manera incompatible con los fines para los que han sido inicialmente recabados, sin perjuicio de las disposiciones legales aplicables de cualquier índole.

Declaro haber recibido toda la información necesaria sobre el tratamiento de datos personales. Confirmando que conozco mis derechos de acceso a cualquier dato personal relacionado conmigo, al igual que mis derechos de modificación o rectificación de estos datos, cancelación, oposición a su uso, así como limitación de su tratamiento. Igualmente, podré retirar mi consentimiento para el uso futuro en cualquier momento y sin justificación alguna.

Para ejercer los derechos mencionados, enviaré una solicitud por escrito a (dirección de correo electrónico del beneficiario que organiza la actividad).

CONSENTIMIENTO ELECTRÓNICO

Por favor, selecciona una opción

Al hacer clic en el botón "Aceptar" declara que

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ha leído la información arriba mencionada</i> 	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Acepta el tratamiento de tus datos personales para participar en el evento</i>
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<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Ha sido claramente informado sobre tus derechos en materia de protección de datos</i>• <i>Acepta participar voluntariamente en el evento</i>• <i>Tiene 18 años o más</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Acepta el uso de tu imagen (vídeos y fotografías) para fines informativos y promocionales de MARINEWIND</i>
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4) GREEK LANGUAGE VERSION

Δια του παρόντος εξουσιοδοτώ τους Δικαιούχους του έργου Horizon Europe MARINEWIND (Grant Agreement Αρ. 101075572) να συλλέγουν, επεξεργάζονται και αποθηκεύουν πληροφορίες σχετικές με το όνομα, το επώνυμο, τις διασυνδέσεις και τα στοιχεία επικοινωνίας μου (e-mail, τηλέφωνο) για έως και δύο χρόνια μετά τη λήξη του έργου για το σκοπό της υλοποίησης του έργου, συγκεκριμένα για την καταγραφή πληροφοριών σχετικά με την εγγραφή και συμμετοχή μου σε συναντήσεις και εκδηλώσεις του έργου (εργαστήρια, διαδικτυακά σεμινάρια, κτλ.), σε έντυπη και ψηφιακή μορφή.

Επίσης εξουσιοδοτώ τους Δικαιούχους του έργου Horizon Europe MARINEWIND να λαμβάνουν φωτογραφίες μου και να καταγράφουν την εικόνα μου σε μορφή βίντεο σε κάθε τοποθεσία όπου λαμβάνουν χώρα συναντήσεις ή δραστηριότητες του έργου, συμπεριλαμβανομένων διαδικτυακών εκδηλώσεων (σε συμμόρφωση με τους κανόνες εμπιστευτικότητας και ασφαλείας του έργου όπως ορίζονται στο Grant Agreement), σε όλη τη διάρκεια του έργου για να χρησιμοποιηθούν για τους σκοπούς αναφοράς και προώθησης του έργου και συναφών δραστηριοτήτων. Με σχέση με αυτό, αυτές οι εικόνες και βίντεο μπορούν να καταγραφούν, να αποθηκευτούν, να υποβληθούν σε επεξεργασία, να αναπαραχθούν, να παρουσιαστούν και να δημοσιευθούν από οποιοδήποτε μέλος της κοινοπραξίας του MARINEWIND καθώς και από οποιοδήποτε τρίτο μέρος που έχει υπογράψει σύμβαση να παράγει το προωθητικό υλικό του έργου, χρησιμοποιώντας οποιοδήποτε είδος μέσων (συμπεριλαμβανομένου έντυπου, υπολογιστικού, οπτικο-ακουστικού, κτλ.), για έως και δύο χρόνια μετά τη λήξη του έργου.

Η πληροφορία που παρέχεται από εμένα κατά τη διάρκεια εκδήλωσης του έργου (π.χ. επαγγελματικές απόψεις) μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν μόνο για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς που σχετίζονται με την υλοποίηση του έργου.

Οι πληροφορίες που παρέχω όπως επίσης και η εικόνα μου δεν θα διαβιβαστούν σε οποιοδήποτε τρίτο μέρος και θα τύχουν επεξεργασίας με τρόπο ασύμβατο με τους σκοπούς για τους οποίους συλλέχθηκαν αρχικά, με την επιφύλαξη οποιασδήποτε ισχύουσας νομικής διάταξης οποιουδήποτε είδους.

Αναγνωρίζω ότι έλαβα όλες τις απαιτούμενες πληροφορίες σχετικά με την επεξεργασία δεδομένων. Επιβεβαιώνω ότι είμαι ενήμερος του δικαιώματός μου για πρόσβαση σε οποιαδήποτε προσωπικά δεδομένα που σχετίζονται με εμένα, του δικαιώματος να τροποποιήσω ή να διορθώσω αυτά τα δεδομένα, να ακυρώσω καθώς και να φέρω αντίρρηση στη χρήση των δεδομένων και να ζητήσω περιορισμό της επεξεργασίας αυτών των δεδομένων. Αναγνωρίζω ότι η νομική βάση που εφαρμόζεται για την επεξεργασία των δεδομένων μου είναι η εξυπηρέτηση των έννομων συμφερόντων των Δικαιούχων του έργου Horizon Europe MARINEWIND καθώς η δημοσίευση φωτογραφιών και βίντεο από τις εκδηλώσεις του έργου είναι αναγκαία για την επίτευξη των στόχων αυτού που σχετίζονται με την επικοινωνία και τη διάδοση των αποτελεσμάτων του.

Για να ασκήσετε τα προαναφερόμενα δικαιώματα, παρακαλώ να στείλετε γραπτό αίτημα στη διεύθυνση info@gplan-intl.gr.

Παρακαλώ κάνετε την επιλογή σας παρακάτω

Πατώντας στο κουμπί «Συμφωνώ» δηλώνετε ότι:

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Έχετε διαβάσει την προαναφερθείσα πληροφορία• Είστε σαφώς ενημερωμένοι σχετικά με τα δικαιώματα προστασίας των δεδομένων σας• Συμφωνείτε οικειοθελώς να συμμετάσχετε στην εκδήλωση• Είστε τουλάχιστον 18 ετών	<ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> Συμφωνώ στην επεξεργασία των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων για το σκοπό της συμμετοχής στην εκδήλωση<input type="checkbox"/> Συμφωνώ στη χρήση της εικόνας μου (βίντεο και φωτογραφίες) για σκοπούς αναφοράς και προώθησης του MARINEWIND
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5) PORTUGUESE LANGUAGE VERSION

Autorizo os Beneficiários do projeto Horizon Europe MARINEWIND (Grant Agreement nº 101075572) a recolher, processar e armazenar informações sobre o meu nome, sobrenome, afiliação e informações de contato (e-mail, número de telefone) por um período até dois anos após o término do projeto com o objetivo de implementação do projeto, nomeadamente para registo de informação sobre a minha inscrição e participação em reuniões e eventos do projeto (workshops, webinars, etc.), em suporte papel e digital.

Autorizo ainda os Beneficiários do projeto Horizon Europe MARINEWIND a tirarem fotografias minhas e a gravarem a minha imagem sob a forma de vídeo em cada local onde decorrem reuniões ou atividades do projeto, incluindo eventos online (sujeito às regras de confidencialidade e segurança do projeto estabelecido no Grant Agreement), durante toda a duração do projeto, a ser usado para fins de relatório e promoção do projeto e atividades relacionadas. Nesse sentido, as fotos e vídeos podem ser gravados, arquivados, processados, reproduzidos, exibidos e publicados publicamente por qualquer membro do consórcio MARINEWIND, bem como por qualquer terceiro contratado para produzir o material promocional do projeto, usando qualquer tipo de mídia (incluindo papel, computador, audiovisual, etc.), até dois anos após o término do projeto.

As informações fornecidas por mim durante o evento do projeto (por exemplo, opiniões profissionais) só podem ser usadas para fins de pesquisa relacionados com a implementação do projeto

As informações por mim fornecidas, bem como a minha imagem, não serão cedidas a terceiros nem tratadas de forma incompatível com as finalidades para as quais foram inicialmente recolhidas, sem prejuízo de qualquer disposição legal aplicável de qualquer natureza.

Reconheço que recebi todas as informações necessárias sobre o processamento de dados. Confirmando que estou ciente do meu direito de acesso a quaisquer dados pessoais que me digam respeito, o direito de modificar ou retificar esses dados, cancelar bem como opor ao uso de dados e solicitar a restrição do processamento desses dados. Também posso retirar o meu consentimento para uso futuro, a qualquer momento, sem qualquer justificação.

Para exercer os direitos acima mencionados, envie um pedido por escrito para (endereço de e-mail do beneficiário que organiza a atividade).

6) FRENCH LANGUAGE VERSION

J'autorise par la présente les bénéficiaires du projet Horizon Europe MARINEWIND (accord de subvention n° 101075572) à collecter, traiter et stocker des informations sur mon nom, prénom, affiliation et coordonnées (e-mail, numéro de téléphone) jusqu'à deux ans après la fin du projet pour le but de la mise en œuvre du projet, notamment pour enregistrer des informations sur mon inscription et ma participation aux réunions et événements du projet (ateliers, webinaires, etc.), sous forme papier et numérique.

J'autorise également les Bénéficiaires du projet Horizon Europe MARINEWIND à prendre des photos de moi et à enregistrer mon image sous forme de vidéo dans chaque lieu où se déroulent des réunions de projet ou des activités de projet, y compris des événements en ligne (sous réserve des règles de confidentialité et de sécurité du projet définis dans la convention de subvention), pendant toute la durée du projet, à utiliser à des fins de rapport et de promotion du projet et des activités affiliées. À cet égard, ces images et vidéos peuvent être enregistrées, stockées, traitées, reproduites, exposées et publiées publiquement par tout membre du consortium MARINEWIND ainsi que par tout tiers engagé pour produire le matériel promotionnel du projet, en utilisant tout type de support (dont papier, informatique, audiovisuel, etc.), jusqu'à deux ans après la fin du projet.

Les informations que j'ai fournies lors de l'événement du projet (par exemple, les avis professionnels) ne peuvent être utilisées qu'à des fins de recherche liées à la mise en œuvre du projet.

Les informations fournies par moi ainsi que mon image ne seront cédées à aucun tiers ni traitées de manière contraire aux finalités pour lesquelles elles ont été initialement collectées, sans préjudice de toute disposition légale applicable de quelque nature que ce soit.

Je reconnais avoir reçu toutes les informations requises sur le traitement des données. Je confirme avoir pris connaissance de mon droit d'accès à toutes les données personnelles me concernant, du droit de modifier ou de rectifier ces données, d'annuler ainsi que de m'opposer à l'utilisation des données et de demander la limitation du traitement de ces données. Je peux également retirer mon consentement pour l'utilisation future à tout moment sans aucune justification.

Pour exercer les droits susmentionnés, veuillez adresser une demande écrite à (adresse e-mail du bénéficiaire organisateur de l'activité).

CONSENTEMENT ÉLECTRONIQUE

*Veuillez sélectionner votre choix ci-dessous
Cliquer sur le bouton "Accepter" indique que*

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vous avez pris connaissance des informations ci-dessus • Vous êtes clairement informé de vos droits en matière de protection des données • Vous acceptez volontairement de participer à l'événement • Vous avez au moins 18 ans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> J'accepte le traitement de mes données personnelles dans le cadre de la participation à l'événement <input type="checkbox"/> J'accepte l'utilisation de mon image (vidéo et photos) à des fins de reportage et de promotion MARINEWIND
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APPENDIX 4 - INFORMED CONSENT USED FOR ONLINE SURVEYS

1) ENGLISH LANGUAGE VERSION

PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this [survey/interview] is voluntary. You may refuse to take part without providing a justification. Please be aware that if you do decide to participate, you may also stop participating at any time without penalty. You have the right to access your data at any time, and the right to modify, rectify, withdraw, or restrict processing of your data until such time the data have been anonymized or analyzed. The data provided by you will not be transferred to any third party nor processed in a manner inconsistent with the purposes for which they have been initially collected, without prejudice to any applicable legal provision of any kind.

BENEFITS

You will receive no direct benefits from participating. However, your responses will help us to complete and improve the MARINEWIND project.

RISKS

There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this [survey/interview]. By answering the questions, you grant permission for the data generated from this questionnaire to be used ONLY for research purposes related to the project implementation and promotion. The results may be disseminated in scientific publications, public reports, blog posts, and other public media wherein anonymity will be guaranteed, unless you have consented to be quoted. Participants' statements may be used in reports as quotes, but in such a way that anonymity is ensured when no explicit consent for citation was given.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your answers and data will be stored in a password-protected electronic format and your responses will remain anonymous. No one outside the MARINEWIND consortium will be able to identify you or your answers, and no one will know you participated in the study.

DATA STORAGE

The collected data will be kept for 2 years after the end of the project and will then be destroyed.

CONTACT

If you have questions about the project or the data protection procedures and/or would like to exercise your data protection rights, you may contact our project coordinator via email at coletta@apre.it.

If you do not agree, you are unfortunately not able to participate in this interview.

ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Please select your choice below.

Clicking on the "Agree" button indicates that:

<ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ You have read the above information.✓ You are clearly informed.✓ You voluntarily agree to participate.✓ Your anonymous answers can be used for research purposes.✓ You are 18 years of age or older.	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree
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Provided that the interviewee confirms that he / she agrees to the Electronic Consent, the interview begins.

2) ITALIAN LANGUAGE VERSION

PARTECIPAZIONE

La sua partecipazione a questo [questionario/intervista] è volontaria. Ha il diritto di rifiutarsi di partecipare senza dover fornire giustificazioni. Sarà possibile decidere di non partecipare in qualsiasi momento senza alcuna penalità. Lei ha il diritto di accedere ai suoi dati in qualsiasi momento, e il diritto di modificarli, di chiederne la rettifica o la restrizione al trattamento prima della loro trasformazione in forma anonima o analisi. I dati da lei forniti non verranno trasferiti a parti terze né trattati in disaccordo con le finalità con cui sono stati raccolti, senza ostare all'applicazione di alcuna disposizione legale.

BENEFICI

Non sono previsti benefici diretti dalla sua partecipazione. Tuttavia, le sue risposte contribuiranno al completamento e al miglioramento del progetto MARINEWIND.

RISCHI

La partecipazione a questo [questionario/intervista] non prevede alcun rischio. Rispondendo alle domande, lei acconsente all'utilizzo dei dati così generati SOLTANTO per finalità di ricerca collegate alla realizzazione e all'avanzamento delle attività progettuali. I risultati potrebbero dare origine a pubblicazioni scientifiche, report pubblici, prodotti di comunicazione (post, articoli, *etc*) nel rispetto dell'anonimato, a patto di previo consenso da parte sua ad essere citato. Nello specifico, le dichiarazioni dei partecipanti potrebbero essere citate nei report di progetto, nel rispetto dell'anonimato, a patto di previo consenso esplicito ad essere citati.

CONFIDENZIALITÀ

Le sue risposte e i dati da lei forniti saranno conservati in formato elettronico protetti da password in un database e le sue risposte rimarranno anonime. Le sue risposte e la sua partecipazione allo studio non saranno rese note al di fuori del consorzio MARINEWIND.

CONSERVAZIONE DEI DATI

I dati raccolti saranno mantenuti per 2 anni dopo la fine del progetto, dopo i quali verranno eliminati.

CONTATTI

In caso di domande sul progetto o sulle procedure di protezione dei dati, e/o per esercitare i suoi diritti di protezione dei dati, può contattare il coordinatore del progetto all'indirizzo email coletta@apre.it.

Il suo consenso al trattamento è necessario per la partecipazione a questo [questionario/intervista]

CONSENSO ELETTRONICO

Selezionare una delle seguenti opzioni.

L'opzione 'Acconsento' indica che:

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Ha letto le informazioni fornite sopra</i>• <i>Ha ricevuto informazioni chiare riguardo i suoi diritti di protezione dei dati</i>• <i>Acconsente volontariamente a partecipare</i>• <i>Le sue risposte in forma anonima possono essere utilizzate con finalità di ricerca</i>• <i>Ha almeno 18 anni</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Acconsento</i>
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3) SPANISH LANGUAGE VERSION

PARTICIPACIÓN

Su participación en esta [encuesta/entrevista] es voluntaria. Puede negarse a participar sin necesidad de justificación. Tenga en cuenta que, si decide participar, también puede dejar de hacerlo en cualquier momento sin penalización alguna. Tiene derecho a acceder a sus datos en cualquier momento, así como a modificarlos, rectificarlos, retirarlos o restringir su tratamiento hasta el momento en que se hayan anonimizado o analizado. Los datos facilitados por usted no se cederán a terceros ni se tratarán de manera incompatible con los fines para los que se recogieron inicialmente, sin perjuicio de las disposiciones legales aplicables de cualquier tipo.

BENEFICIOS

No recibirá ningún beneficio directo por participar. Sin embargo, sus respuestas nos ayudarán a completar y mejorar el proyecto MARINEWIND.

RIESGOS

No existen riesgos previsibles al participar en esta [encuesta/entrevista]. Al responder a las preguntas, usted autoriza que los datos generados a partir de este cuestionario se utilicen ÚNICAMENTE con fines de investigación relacionados con la ejecución y promoción del proyecto. Los resultados podrán difundirse en publicaciones científicas, informes públicos, entradas de blog y otros medios de comunicación públicos en los que se garantizará el anonimato, a menos que usted haya consentido que se le cite. Las declaraciones de los participantes podrán utilizarse en los informes como citas, pero de forma que se garantice el anonimato cuando éstos no hayan dado un consentimiento explícito para ello.

CONFIDENCIALIDAD

Sus respuestas y datos se almacenarán en un formato electrónico protegido por contraseña y sus respuestas permanecerán anónimas. Nadie ajeno al consorcio MARINEWIND podrá identificarle a usted ni a sus respuestas, y nadie sabrá que ha participado en el estudio.

ALMACENAJE DE DATOS

Los datos recogidos se conservarán durante dos (2) años tras la finalización del proyecto y después se destruirán.

CONTACTO

Si usted tiene alguna duda sobre el proyecto o el tratamiento de sus datos y/o desea ejercer sus derechos de protección de datos, puede ponerse en contacto con nuestra coordinadora del proyecto por correo electrónico en coletta@apre.it. Si no está de acuerdo, lamentablemente no podrá participar en esta [encuesta/entrevista].

CONSENTIMIENTO ELECTRÓNICO

Por favor, seleccione una de las siguientes opciones

Al hacer clic en el botón "Aceptar" declara que

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Ha leído la información arriba mencionada</i>• <i>Ha sido claramente informado</i>• <i>Acepta participar voluntariamente en el evento</i>• <i>Sus respuesta anónimas pueden ser utilizadas para propósitos de investigación</i>• <i>Tiene 18 años o más</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Acepto</i>
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4) GREEK LANGUAGE VERSION

ΣΥΜΜΕΤΟΧΗ

Η συμμετοχή σας σε αυτή την [έρευνα/ συνέντευξη] είναι εθελοντική. Μπορείτε να αρνηθείτε να συμμετάσχετε χωρίς να παρέχετε αιτιολόγηση. Παρακαλώ, λάβετε υπόψη ότι εάν αποφασίσετε να συμμετάσχετε, μπορείτε επίσης να διακόψετε τη συμμετοχή οποιαδήποτε στιγμή χωρίς ποινή. Έχετε το δικαίωμα πρόσβασης στα δεδομένα σας οποιαδήποτε στιγμή και το δικαίωμα να τροποποιήσετε, να διορθώσετε και να περιορίσετε την επεξεργασία των δεδομένων σας έως ότου τα δεδομένα καταστούν ανώνυμα ή αναλυθούν. Τα δεδομένα που παρέχονται από εσάς δεν θα διαβιβαστούν σε τρίτους, ούτε θα υποβληθούν σε επεξεργασία με τρόπο που δεν συνάδει με τους σκοπούς για τους οποίους έχουν αρχικά συλλεχθεί, με την επιφύλαξη οποιασδήποτε ισχύουσας νομικής διάταξης οποιουδήποτε είδους. Η νομική βάση που χρησιμοποιείται για την επεξεργασία των δεδομένων σας είναι η εξυπηρέτηση των έννομων συμφερόντων των Δικαιούχων του έργου Horizon Europe MARINEWIND καθώς η πραγματοποίηση της [έρευνας/ συνέντευξης] είναι αναγκαία για την ομαλή υλοποίηση του έργου σύμφωνα με τις συμβατικές απαιτήσεις αυτού. Μόνο σε περίπτωση κατά την οποία χρειαστεί να χρησιμοποιήσουμε τα δεδομένα σας ονομαστικά, και όχι ανώνυμα, θα ζητήσουμε τη συναίνεση σας (ως νομική βάση επεξεργασίας) επικοινωνώντας εκ νέου μαζί σας για το σκοπό αυτό.

ΟΦΕΛΗ

Δεν θα λάβετε άμεσα οφέλη από τη συμμετοχή. Ωστόσο, οι απαντήσεις σας θα μας βοηθήσουν να ολοκληρώσουμε και να βελτιώσουμε το έργο MARINEWIND.

ΚΙΝΔΥΝΟΙ

Δεν υπάρχουν προβλέψιμοι κίνδυνοι από τη συμμετοχή σε αυτή την [έρευνα/ συνέντευξη]. Απαντώντας τις ερωτήσεις, παραχωρείτε άδεια για τα δεδομένα που παράγονται από αυτό το ερωτηματολόγιο να χρησιμοποιηθούν ΜΟΝΟ για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς που σχετίζονται με την υλοποίηση και προώθηση του έργου. Τα αποτελέσματα μπορεί να διαδοθούν σε επιστημονικές δημοσιεύσεις, δημόσιες αναφορές, αναρτήσεις ιστού και άλλα δημόσια μέσα ενημέρωσης στα οποία η ανωνυμία θα είναι εγγυημένη, εκτός εάν έχετε συναινέσει να σας αναφέρουν. Οι δηλώσεις των συμμετεχόντων μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν σε αναφορές ως παράθεση αλλά με τέτοιο τρόπο ώστε η ανωνυμία να διασφαλίζεται όταν δεν έχει δοθεί ρητή συγκατάθεση για αναφορά.

ΕΜΠΙΣΤΕΥΤΙΚΟΤΗΤΑ

Οι απαντήσεις και τα δεδομένα σας θα αποθηκευτούν σε ηλεκτρονική μορφή που προστατεύεται με κωδικό και οι απαντήσεις σας θα παραμείνουν ανώνυμες. Κανένας εκτός της κοινοπραξίας του MARINEWIND δεν θα μπορεί να αναγνωρίσει εσάς ή τις απαντήσεις σας και κανένας δεν θα γνωρίζει ότι συμμετείχατε στη μελέτη.

ΑΠΟΘΗΚΕΥΣΗ ΔΕΔΟΜΕΝΩΝ

Τα δεδομένα που θα συλλεχθούν θα διατηρηθούν για 2 χρόνια μετά τη λήξη του έργου και στη συνέχεια θα καταστραφούν.

ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΑ

Εάν έχετε ερωτήσεις σχετικά με το έργο ή τις διαδικασίες προστασίας δεδομένων και/ή θα θέλατε να ασκήσετε τα δικαιώματά σας προστασίας δεδομένων, μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε με το συντονιστή του έργου μας μέσω e-mail στην ηλεκτρονική διεύθυνση coletta@apre.it.

Εάν δεν συμφωνείτε, δυστυχώς δεν μπορείτε να συμμετάσχετε σε αυτή τη συνέντευξη.

Παρακαλώ κάνετε την επιλογή σας παρακάτω

Πατώντας στο κουμπί «Συμφωνώ» δηλώνετε ότι:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Έχετε διαβάσει την προαναφερθείσα πληροφορία. • Είστε σαφώς ενημερωμένοι. • Συμφωνείτε οικειοθελώς να συμμετάσχετε. • Οι ανώνυμες απαντήσεις σας μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν για ερευνητικούς σκοπούς. • Είστε 18 ετών ή μεγαλύτεροι. 	<input type="checkbox"/> Συμφωνώ
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5) PORTUGUESE LANGUAGE VERSION

PARTICIPAÇÃO

A sua participação neste [questionário/entrevista] é voluntária. Você tem o direito de se recusar a participar sem ter que apresentar justificção. Pode decidir não participar a qualquer momento sem qualquer penalidade. Tem o direito de aceder aos seus dados a qualquer momento, bem como o direito de modificá-los, solicitar a retificação ou restrição de processamento antes da sua transformação em forma anónima ou análise. Os dados que fornecer não serão cedidos a terceiros nem tratados em desacordo com as finalidades para que foram recolhidos, sem prejuízo da aplicação de qualquer disposição legal.

BENEFÍCIOS

Nenhum benefício direto é esperado de sua participação. No entanto, as suas respostas contribuirão para a conclusão e melhoria do projeto MARINEWIND.

RISCOS

A participação neste [questionário/entrevista] não envolve nenhum risco. Ao responder às perguntas, você concorda com o uso dos dados assim gerados APENAS para fins de pesquisa relacionados com a implementação e andamento das atividades do projeto. Os resultados podem dar origem a publicações científicas, relatórios públicos, produtos de comunicação (postagens, artigos, etc.) respeitando o anonimato, desde que você dê o seu consentimento prévio para ser citado. Especificamente, as falas dos participantes poderão ser citadas nos relatórios do projeto, respeitando o anonimato, mediante prévio consentimento explícito para serem citadas.

CONFIDENCIALIDADE

As suas respostas e os dados que fornecer serão armazenados num formato eletrónico protegido por senha num banco de dados e as suas respostas permanecerão anónimas. As suas respostas e participação no estudo não serão divulgadas fora do consórcio MARINEWIND.

RETENÇÃO DE DADOS

Os dados recolhidos serão conservados durante 2 anos após o final do projeto, após o quale serão eliminados.

CONTATOS

Se tiver alguma dúvida sobre o projeto ou os procedimentos de proteção de dados e/ou para exercer seus direitos de proteção de dados, entre em contato com o coordenador do projeto através do endereço coletta@apre.it.

O seu consentimento para o processamento é necessário para a participação neste [questionário/entrevista]

CONSENTIMENTO ELETRÔNICO

Selecione uma das seguintes opções.

A opção 'Concordo' significa que:

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Leu as informações fornecidas acima</i>• <i>Recebeu informações claras sobre seus os direitos de proteção de dados</i>• <i>Concorda voluntariamente em participar</i>• <i>As suas respostas anónimas podem ser usadas para fins de pesquisa</i>• <i>Tem pelo menos 18 anos</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Concordo</i>
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6) FRENCH LANGUAGE VERSION

PARTICIPATION

Votre participation à ce [questionnaire/entretien] est volontaire. Vous avez le droit de refuser de participer sans vous justifier. Veuillez noter que si vous décidez de participer, vous pouvez également arrêter de participer à tout moment sans pénalité. Vous avez le droit d'accéder à vos données à tout moment, et le droit de les modifier, rectifier, retirer ou restreindre le traitement de vos données jusqu'à ce que les données aient été anonymisées ou analysées. Les données que vous fournissez ne seront pas cédées à aucun tiers ou traitées de manière contraire aux finalités pour lesquelles elles ont été collectées, sans préjudice de toute disposition légale applicable de quelque nature que ce soit.

AVANTAGES

Aucun avantage direct n'est attendu de votre participation. Cependant, vos réponses contribueront à la réalisation et à l'amélioration du projet MARINEWIND.

DES RISQUES

Il n'y a aucun risque prévisible lié à la participation à cette [enquête/entretien]. En répondant aux questions, vous autorisez l'utilisation des données générées à partir de ce questionnaire UNIQUEMENT à des fins de recherche liées à la mise en œuvre et à l'avancement des activités du projet. Les résultats pourront donner lieu à des publications scientifiques, des rapports publics, des produits de communication (posts, articles, etc.) dans le respect de l'anonymat, à condition que vous donniez votre accord préalable pour être cité. En particulier, les déclarations des participants pourraient être citées dans les rapports de projet, dans le respect de l'anonymat, sous réserve d'un consentement explicite préalable à être cité.

CONFIDENTIALITÉ

Vos réponses et les données que vous fournissez seront stockées dans un format électronique protégé par un mot de passe dans une base de données et vos réponses resteront anonymes. Vos réponses et votre participation à l'étude ne seront pas divulguées en dehors du consortium MARINEWIND.

LA CONSERVATION DES DONNÉES

Les données collectées seront conservées pendant 2 ans après la fin du projet, après quoi elles seront supprimées.

CONTACTS

Si vous avez des questions sur le projet ou les procédures de protection des données, et/ou pour exercer vos droits de protection des données, vous pouvez contacter le coordinateur du projet à l'adresse e-mail coletta@apre.it.

Votre consentement au traitement est nécessaire pour participer à ce [questionnaire/entretien]

CONSENTEMENT ÉLECTRONIQUE

*Veillez sélectionner votre choix ci-dessous
Cliquer sur le bouton "Accepter" indique que*

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Vous avez lu les informations fournies ci-dessus</i>• <i>Vous avez reçu des informations claires sur vos droits en matière de protection des données</i>• <i>Accepte volontairement de participer</i>• <i>Vos réponses anonymes peuvent être utilisées à des fins de recherche</i>• <i>A au moins 18 ans</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> J'accepte
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